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TYOLOGY OF METHODS OF TRANSLATING RAY BRADBURY'S PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS INTO RUSSIAN (BASED ON THE STORIES "MARTIAN CHRONICLES")

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Abstract

The relevance of the research is determined by the need for a comprehensive study of phraseological units related to the genre of science fiction. The purpose of the study is to analyze Ray Bradbury's phraseological units in a translational aspect. The system of methods includes the method of continuous sampling and comparative lexico-stylistic analysis. Conclusions. The following methods of interlanguage transformation were used in the translation: the method of partial and full equivalent; descriptive; overtone translation; literal translation; omission.

Keywords: phraseological units, translation, interlanguage transformation.

Phraseological units in the works of Ray Bradbury are of considerable interest for scientific research. They allow you to focus the reader's attention on the inner world of the characters, make monologues, dialogues and the plot as a whole more dynamic. However, the idiosyncrasies of the writer and the context of the use of phraseological phrases create difficulties when translating them into Russian.

We have considered the variants of the translation of phraseological units presented by T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov in the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles" [2]. The analysis of the methods of transformation of phraseological units used by the above-mentioned authors was carried out according to the classification of A.V. Kunin [4]. As a result, the following methods were identified: the method of full equivalent; the method of partial equivalent; descriptive method; literal translation (calculus); overtone translation; omission of phraseological turnover in the translation text.

The group of phraseological units, in the translation of which the method of full equivalent is used, usually includes expressions of an international nature based on national traditions, customs and historical facts. The number of such correspondences in the work "Martian Chronicles" is not numerous:

'To the devil with him!' – Gone, and the hell with it!

'Long time no see!' – Haven't seen you for a long time!

'I think we're on the right track now'. "I think we're on the right track."

'Thank the Lord you had your own private rockets'. – Thank God you have your own rockets.

'Now one clock was set in motion, a faint ticking' – One mechanism ticked softly, the input started.

We also noted that when translating phraseological units, additional information was added to them. At the same time, not only the stylistic, but also the emotional coloring of phraseological turns changes. For example, in the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles" we meet the phraseology 'Out with it, you!', which in translation looks like "Spread it!".

Phraseology 'Out with it!' is defined in Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary' as follows: 'Said to someone when you want them to tell you something they don't want you to know' [5, p.1008]. The Russian verb "to spread out" in accordance with Dmitriev's "Explanatory Dictionary" means "to talk openly and directly about something" [3, p. 103].

When translating phraseological phrases into Russian, in a number of cases, the method of partial equivalent is used. A partial equivalent does not mean any incompleteness in the transmission of meaning, but only contains lexical, grammatical or lexico-grammatical discrepancies in the presence of the same meaning of the same stylistic orientation.

When translating the cycle of stories "The Martian Chronicles", T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov try to adhere as closely as possible to the original, observing, among other things, the stylistic orientation of the work. In most of the examples of phraseological units we have studied by the partial equivalent method, they convey the meaning of verbs and participles very accurately, but allow lexical discrepancies in the case of other parts of speech. For example, 'Sir, I thought we might break out rations of gin and meat and whoop it up a bit'. – Boss, it would be nice to open a few cans of gin and meat and have a little fun.

The expression 'Whoop it up' means 'to enjoy yourself in a noisy and excited way', 'noisy fun' and refers to slang vocabulary. The verb "to carouse" used by the translators – "to get drunk in a riotous company" is also slang. In the context of the story, it is used to draw readers' attention to the joy of astronauts from the fact that after a long and dangerous journey, they still reached Mars.

The method of descriptive translation is used by translators to explain the meaning of a phraseological unit that has neither a partial nor a full equivalent in the Russian language and is not subject to literal translation. This method of translating phraseological units is also used in the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles" in the following examples:

'Of all the silly, exasperating things'. The captain chewed a cigar as he waited'. – Everything has happened in my sinful life, but this... The captain waited, chewing on his cigar.

'If anything happens they can get the hell out'. – If something happens, they will have time to get away.

'It scares the hell out of me.' – I'm scared, you know, scared!

To transfer phraseological phrases with a transparent word-formation structure into Russian, translators also use calculus or literal translation.

In the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles", a literal translation is used in relation to phraseological units with an understandable internal form that cannot be preserved by other methods:

'You're mixed up'. – And you got something wrong.

'Then, for curiosity's sake, you'd better come in and look around' – In that case, for curiosity's sake, they would.

Overtone versions of phraseological units are used by translators only in a certain context, due to the events occurring in the works. The presence of examples of the use of this method of translation indicates that all translators are trying in the best way, from their point of view, to convey to Russian-speaking readers the thoughts, feelings and experiences of the main characters of the works.

Let's consider an example of an overtone translation in the cycle of stories "The Martian Chronicles". 'Just as you put a stake through the heart of Halloween and told your film producers that if they made anything at all they would have to make and remake Earnest Hemingway'. – You also dealt with all the miracle workers; and you also ordered your film producers, if they want to do anything at all, let them shoot and reshoot Ernest Hemingway.

'To put a stake through the heart' is defined as 'to try to harm' [5, p. 1157] and is translated into Russian as "to kill". English phraseology is an analogue of the verb "to crack down" – 'to crack down' [1, p. 372]. However, T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov take into account the specifics of the context and emphasize the emotionality of the speech of the main character of one of the stories "Chronicles". He is outraged that representatives of the totalitarian regime established on Mars ruthlessly destroy all books, films and works of art.

During the research, we also noted cases of omission of phraseological units in the translation texts.

'It's settled. I won't go'. – I'm not going.

'Up and down green wine canals, boats as delicate as bronze flowers drifted'. – Boats were gliding through the green moisture of the canals.

Examples of the omission of phraseology are also present in the stories of the collection "Mechanisms of Joy": 'Time and again she called to him, demanding that he summon her a shore'. – Then she would start shouting with all her might: come, my love, and take me ashore!

Speaking about the methods of translating phraseological units in the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles", it can be stated that the method of partial equivalent is most often used (52% of cases or 34 FE out of 65). This fact is explained by the fact that translators T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov try to stick to the original and at the same time preserve the stylistic orientation of Ray Bradbury's work. In the translation text, they use phraseological units that coincide in meaning, imagery, lexical composition with the phraseological units of the original text, but still differ in such features as the number and order of words.

According to our conclusions, the method of partial equivalent in the translation of phraseological units within this work is used for the following purposes: to convey the emotional coloring of the unit or to replace sayings and colloquial-abusive expressions peculiar to another culture with equivalents close to the Russian reader.

The full equivalent method is the second most frequently used by translators (17% of cases or 11 FE out of 65). This method is used by translators in relation to expressions of an international nature based on national traditions, customs and historical facts, as well as on the common human experience of native speakers of English and Russian. In some cases, additional emotionality is introduced into the equivalents of the translation text.

The descriptive translation method is the third most frequently used (14% of cases or 9 FE out of 65). Translators resort to it in order to explain the meaning of phraseological units if it is impossible to carry out a literal translation within the framework of the Russian language. At the same time, one way or another, there is an undesirable change in the style of the text.

The frequency of using a literal translation is 5% of cases or 3 FE out of 65. Its use is justified, since the images contained in a stable combination are not indifferent to the understanding of the text, and replacing them in another way does not give sufficient effect. The overtone translation is noted in 9% of cases and is due only to the context and the decision of the translators not to use the generally accepted equivalent of a particular phraseology.

Omission of phraseological units in the translation text, found in 3% of cases (only 2 examples out of 65). Translators used this method in relation to those phraseological units, the translation of which would lead to a violation of the norms of the Russian language in the sentence. At the same time, their omission in no way affected the semantic component of the text.

Within the framework of this research work, the quantitative correlation of methods of translating phraseological units of the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles" into Russian was also analyzed according to the classification of A.V. Kunin. As described above, in accordance with the typology of A.V. Kunin, there are two types of translation methods: phraseological and non-phraseological. The first type includes the method of full and partial equivalents, and the second type – overtone translation, literal translation (calculus) and descriptive translation. If it is impossible to translate, it is possible to omit phraseology.

As a result of the analysis, we came to the conclusion that T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov used phraseological methods in 69% of cases (45 FE out of 65) and non-phraseological methods of translation in 31% of

cases (20 FE out of 65) when recreating the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles".

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INDIRECTNESS AS AN EFFECTIVE STRATEGY OF POLITE BEHAVIOUR IN W. S. MAUGHAM'S "THEATRE"

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Abstract

Nowadays, one of the key aspects of interpersonal communication is polite behaviour towards the interlocutor achieved in various ways, namely through indirect speech acts. The present paper highlights the importance of indirectness or vagueness as a manifestation of polite behaviour while telling someone to do something from a perspective of negative politeness. A considerable amount of attention is paid to indirect requests which primarily aim at saving the hearer's negative face through mitigating face threatening acts (FTAs). The appropriate degree of politeness in indirect speech acts largely depends on some social scales, more specifically, Distance, Power and Rank of imposition. The higher the weightiness of imposition is, the politer the indirect request is supposed to be.

Keywords: indirect request, 'tell-someone-to-do' utterance, positive and negative face, face threatening acts, negative politeness, vertical and horizontal distance, cost-benefit scale, optionality.

In modern world, which significantly lacks mutual understanding and compromise, the ability to convey one's thoughts, ideas or desires clearly and appropriately without any attempt of imposition on others' wishes or actions is of great significance. While interacting with others we may have various intentions the realizations of which very often depend not only on ourselves as speakers but also on a number of linguistic and extralinguistic factors which vary considerably from context to context. These two levels which are reciprocally dependent on each other are equally important to better understand different manifestations of the three metafunctions of the language (ideational, interpersonal, textual), which Halliday ascribes to grammar [4, 38-39]. These metafunctions are intricately intertwined and serve as a solid base to better perceive the world around us (ideational metafunction); to express different viewpoints, feelings, attitudes and emotions when communicating with others (interpersonal metafunction); and to arrange the propositional content

into a coherent whole (textual metafunction) [2, 4]. Accordingly, the aim of any communicative act differs, as do its manifestations and interpretations. In order to make the communication process more collaborative and effective we need to follow some basic conversational norms and principles characteristic of different situational contexts. Herein lies the importance of the Cooperative Principle with its four Maxims (the Maxims of Quantity, Quality, Relation and Manner) put forth by P. Grice [3, 42]. However, the extent to which these maxims are to be followed or violated by the participants is primarily determined and regulated by certain circumstances. Surprising though it may seem, a full or partial infringement of this or that maxim is justified when interlocutors are obliged to sound less cooperative than is required for the sake of politeness or speech etiquette, both of which act as discourse-regulating devices especially when it comes to the right use of the language and its tools in a specific situation and environment. Thus, depending on the purpose of com-